

Polyfōnía: an Interactive Vocal Processing System using Finger Tracking

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ABSTRACT

Traditional foot-controlled vocal processors are not oriented towards the real-time needs of vocal performers, as their handling method interferes with the posture and expressiveness of the performers' body, acting more like a communication barrier and a source of distraction. Polyfōnía is a real-time portable vocal processing system, which can be controlled by means of finger gestures without the use of gloves or the need for wiring. Its vocal processors include a live looping system and a harmonizer. Motion detection is performed using a motion sensor. Through specific gestures, users can develop and control real-time voice harmonies and live looping. The system takes as input audio signals from a microphone and outputs a processed version of the input. The goal of Polyfōnía is to offer a more natural handling of vocal processors, through new technologies and interactive performance, eliminating the need for added components and making real-time vocal processing a valuable tool for artists. It is intended to be used in conjunction with the vocalists' standard performing techniques and aesthetics, as a means for expanding the creative possibilities of the human voice.

1. INTRODUCTION

Interactive experiences can be classified into different taxonomies, depending on the participants' level of engagement with the artworks [1] or on their reliance or independence of past information [2]. Analysis of the different types of interaction, in combination with a deeper understanding of their changing nature, could lead to the optimization of the interactive music systems, thus providing richer user experiences and a significant expanse of the artistic creation scope. The idea behind the design of Polyfōnía is the development of an interactive system for controlling digital audio effects, that would be consistent with the interpretation of phonetic music, i.e., in complete harmony with both its kinesiological terms and its performance requirements.

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According to Luck and Toiviainen [3], the position of a singer's upper body and the inclination of their head have a significant effect on the quality of their voice, while normal postural alignment optimizes their vocal performance, in terms of vocal technique [4–6]. The operation of foot-controlled digital processors poses specific demands (i.e. altering one's body posture and tilting their head), many of which adapt more to the instrumentalists' needs. In music genres where the essence of the vocal performance is borne by the optimization of one's vocal technique, expressive austerity, or theatrical interpretation, controlling processors through pedals, knobs, or even midi keyboards often creates additional needs, and, in the latter case, assumes prior musical training/expertise, rather than embracing the performance in a natural manner.

The key-requirements in the design of interaction parameters in Polyfōnía are:

- operational without the use of cables, gloves, or bulky devices
- tracking of both hands
- use of hand-gestures that are easy to remember and congruent with the performers' normal postural alignment, thus not interfering with their expressive body movement
- operational in low-light conditions
- immediate and efficient system response, not requiring the use of a display

These design requirements lead to a system assisting users control vocal polyphonic creation in real time, even in poor light conditions, with the best accuracy, using the simplest possible equipment.

Although there is extensive literature on voice gesture-controllers, presented in the next section, there is a significant gap in the implementation of voice polyphonic controllers that would not rely on the use of gloves or wiring. The motivation for this research was the possibility of polyphonic interpretation of traditional Greek songs, live, on stage, without the use of additional cabling equipment, so that such a task could be integrated with the aesthetics and the simplicity of this type of music.

The novelty and contribution of this work consists in the following: (i) creating a gesture-controlled system for the

production of voice polyphony without using gloves, joysticks, midi keyboard, or wiring (ii) designing the gestures and functionality that would support the simplicity in the application use and would not require extensive user-training. (iii) ensuring the extendability of the system, allowing users to add operations and enrich its use.

2. RELATED WORK

Motion-capture is a contemporary tool utilized in expressive music interpretation systems [7] since the sophisticated movements used in human-computer interaction make it an efficient method for controlling expressive parameters. Sensors or computer vision algorithms have been used creatively for decades [8–10]. Examples of such creative control systems are listed in this section.

In 2003, Dobrian and Bevilacqua [11] developed a gestural control system for music, which received data from Vicom 8. The system input required the circular placement of eight cameras around the user. Another large-scale system was Pamela Z [12], which uses extended vocal techniques and live, body-controlled electronic processing from solo events to large-scale works that combine video, audio, and live musicians / singers / actors.

Wearable devices have also been used in the context of creative gestural controllers. For example, in 2009 Jessop [13] created a gesture-based wearable controller for live vocal performances, the Vocal Augmentation and Manipulation Prosthesis (VAMP), allowing singers to capture and manipulate single notes. In a similar concept, Gualtieri et al. [14] and Feugère et al. [15] have proposed the PLS and Chorus Digitalis polyphonic gestural singing systems, respectively, which operate using gloves, joysticks, and graphic tablets. In 2018, Tavares et al. [16] introduced the WMTSensor-GloveNorderval, a data-glove used in an opera performance to control audiovisual elements on stage through gestural movements. This glove-like wireless wearable controller can communicate with a multitude of software through Open Sound Control (OSC) messages.

Sound spatialization is another field that has been explored in this context. In 2009, Smallwood et al. [17] developed a hemispherical 6-speaker system that mimics the way acoustic musical instruments emit sound in all directions, which users could control with vertical and horizontal movements. Berthaut et al. [18] designed a virtual multi-process immersive instrument to create audio events in musical environments using 3D audiovisual objects.

In [19], Hantrakul and Kaczmarek mention the $[A]^2$ project, which uses a system based on the Leap Motion Controller that modulates the effects of a live remix using sampled recordings of a preceding performance and a 5-grain granular synthesizer. The system, which is built in Max/MSP, allows users to trigger individual audio grains through finger motion. Abacus is another Max/MSP operated system developed on an Arduino Teensy built by Warren [20]. It tracks vocal gestures and uses them to adjust various musical parameters including rhythm, pitch, and noise.

Norderval et al. have focused on the use of sound technologies as a prosthesis to the vocal body [21] and the acoustic and aesthetic conflicts between opera and electroacoustic music [22]. Their system is based on Max/MSP and a variety of controllers such as the Leap Motion, smart phones, the HotHand wearable ring etc. In a similar concept, Eriksson et al. have studied the movement-based interactions, implementing an opera where custom-built drones are performing on stage alongside human performers [23], analysing how movements enabled by the human-drone assemblage can affect the artistic expressions [24].

3. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Polyfōnía consists of a Max/MSP standalone patch with two main Interaction Modules, each associated with a Vocal Processor, and a Motion Skeletal Tracking component. Its two vocal processors are the Live Looping Module and the Harmonizer Module. Polyfōnía’s simple architecture, requires a Leap motion controller, a microphone, and a computer. The audio input from the microphone is routed to the Vocal Processors. The input sensor data collected from the motion controller passes through the Motion Skeletal Tracking component to the main Interaction Modules. The audio signal is modified by the Processors depending on the Interaction Module output. The implementation can be found here [25].

Figure 1. System architecture: The audio signal is the input to the live looping and the harmonizer modules, described in 3.4. The sensor data, extracted from the Leap Motion, is the input of the two interaction modules, described in 3.5. Each of the two interaction modules controls one of the vocal processors. The final processed audio signal is routed to MAX/MSP for output.

3.1 The Motion Controller

The motion detector that was used was the well-known off-the-shelf Leap Motion Controller, designed by Leap Mo-

Interaction Area
2 feet above the controller, by 2 feet wide on each side (150° angle), by 2 feet deep on each side (120° angle)

Figure 2. The Leap Motion Interaction Area [29]

Figure 3. The Leap Motion right-handed coordinate system [30]

tion Inc and released in 2013 [26]. It recognizes movements of hands, fingers, and objects that resemble them and it is designed to perceive motion as users naturally move their hands [7]. Leap Motion has a sub-millimeter accuracy, allowing a position accuracy of 0.2 mm, tested with an industrial robot with a reference pen [27]. Although they are other motion controllers, e.g. the Kinect created by Microsoft (2013), the IC Air created by Steinberg (2013) or the iRing created by IK Multimedia, the reason behind selecting the Leap Motion was that comparable controllers in the same price range, were not able to achieve its accuracy [27].

The device operates at close range with high precision and high frame-rate and is also able to detect finger positions, palm orientation, gestures and movement. The controller connects via the computer's USB port and uses optical sensors and infrared light. The sensors are directed to the vertical axis with an opening of 150 degrees and the distance from the controller varies between 25 and 600 mm from the device. In terms of hardware, it consists of two cameras and three infrared leds. Infrared leds are able to detect wavelengths of 850 nm [28]. Thanks to its wide-angle lens, the controller has a large, inverted, pyramid-shaped interaction space (8 cubic feet).

The Leap Motion software combines its sensor data with an internal model of the human hand coping with challeng-

Figure 4. IRCAM's "Leap Motion Skeletal Tracking in Max" output data example

ing tracking conditions [30]. For the detection purposes, a right-handed Cartesian coordinate system is used, with the origin centered at the top of the Leap Motion Controller. The x- and z-axes lie in the horizontal plane, with the x-axis running parallel to the long edge of the device [30]. It uses an infrared stereo cameras as a tracking sensor. For data processing the controller applies advanced algorithms to the raw sensor data, which bypass the background and lighting, and perform analysis for the three-dimensional representation of the operator's hands.

3.2 Skeletal Tracking

The "Leap Motion Skeletal Tracking in Max" patch was implemented by IRCAM [31] and was used for interfacing MAX/MSP with the motion controller. This patch takes as input the motion controller sensor data and outputs data collected from the motion controller (Figure 4). In particular, it returns 3D numerical data retrieved by the SDK of the leap motion controller, concerning the user's hands (position, direction, velocity, strength, etc), wrists and fingers (tip position, velocity, direction etc), as described in detail in the Leap Motion SDK [32, 33]. This information is displayed in the form of numeric variables in the MAX / MSP environment, usable by the user for the design and definition of novel gestures.

3.3 Gestures

New gestures had to be designed, since the ones recognised by the existing Leap Motion SDK Library (CircleGesture, KeyTapGesture, ScreenTapGesture, SwipeGesture, etc.) [30] were not compatible with the natural movement of the performer's body and hands. Most of them were designed to simulate the control of smartphones or tablets.

The gesture dictionary was designed and implemented so that a musician can easily recall and activate the desired musical intervals and operations. Each gesture functions as a "pose", or "a static gesture", as it activates or deactivates prespecified toggles, thus enabling easy control of Polyfonia's live looping or harmonizer module which offers up to fourteen parallel voices. As per Mitra et al. [34] a gesture can be static or dynamic. Thus, for the sake of convenience we call them all simply "gestures".

By opening or closing both one's hands, users can activate or deactivate the system.

By closing one's left hand, users can activate the live looping module. The live-looping control gestures are designed to emulate a more natural movement of "grabbing" and "releasing" the sound.

Using one’s right hand fingers, a user can enable the harmonizer module, thus creating musical intervals from minor second to major ninth. The position of the hand (to the left or right of the central axis of the controller, as described in Table 1), can indicate a smaller or a bigger musical interval. For the harmonizer processor, we set the performer’s options to activate and deactivate voices via toggles (rather than keeping voices active throughout the duration of each movement). The motivation for a discretely control was the ability that multiple voices could be manipulated simultaneously with a few movements. In addition, the importance of the gestures’ easy memorization and thus, the numbers of the musical intervals were used so that there can be a direct correspondence with the musical intervals.

Figure 5 shows the gesture vocabulary, Figure 6 shows the toggles that activate or deactivate each of 14 voices and Table 1 shows the suggested configuration, which is mentioned in the Evaluation section. However, it is important to mention that the performer can easily assign any gesture to any pitch shifting, simply by modifying the number of semitones for the chosen toggle in the Max/MSP patch, thus changing the musical interval that each gesture activates.

3.4 Polyfōnía Live Looping and Harmonizer Modules

The live looping processor consists of a live looper which permits live audio recording from the input microphone and play it on repeat, controlled by toggles. The harmonizer processor can perform pitch shifting on the input acoustic signal. It can pitch-shift the input signal to match the twelve halftones of the european twelve-tone scale, with a separate toggle switch to enable or disable each of the voices. The implementation of vocal processor components is not within the scope of the proposed work. For the Polyfōnía field testing we made modifications of basic Max/MSP audio processors originated from the Max/MSP’s library and forum. However, the Polyfōnía’s main interaction modules can work with any loop activated with toggles and any up-to-14-voices harmonizer, enabling and disabling each of its voices with a toggle.

3.5 Polyfōnía Interaction Modules

The Live-looping Interaction Module and the Harmonizer Interaction Module constitute the core of the system and the algorithm was implemented by the authors in Max/MSP. These two modules are responsible for the real-time interaction between the user and the parametrization of the digital processing units through the user’s hand movements, as described in the previous section. They take the data from the Skeletal Tracking component as input, calculate the distances between all of the fingers’ positions involved in each movement, and make the corresponding changes in the Vocal Processors. The variables used in this module include fingers’ tip position, grab strength (the strength of a grab hand pose) and orientation of both user hands.

Semitones	Interval	Gesture (Side)
1	Minor second	II (LEFT)
2	Major second	II (RIGHT)
3	Minor Third	III (LEFT)
4	Major Third	III (RIGHT)
5	Perfect Fourth	IV (LEFT)
6	Augmented Fourth	IV (RIGHT)
7	Perfect Fifth	V (LEFT)
8	Augmented Fifth	V (RIGHT)
9	Major Sixth	VI (LEFT)
10	Augmented Sixth	VI (RIGHT)
11	Major Seventh	VII (LEFT)
12	Octave	VII (RIGHT)
13	Augmented Eight	VIII (LEFT)
14	Ninth	VIII (RIGHT)

Table 1. The correspondence between the gestures and the music intervals.

The Live-looping Interaction Module controls the live-looping processor (i.e. starts and stops playback of the recorded signal) with the predefined hand gestures. For the previous mentioned gestures recognition, we analysed the data regarding the intensity of the grab for both hands.

Regarding the handling of the Harmonizer Processor, the performer can enable or disable each voice switch with a predefined gesture (Figure 6). This module recognises seven movements, each of which activates a separate voice if formed to the left or right of the vertical axis starting from the center of the motion controller. Therefore, as shown in Table 1, the vocal performer can activate up to fourteen parallel voices, creating the desired harmony effect.

The implementation of Polyfōnía, and demo of its use, can be found here ¹ [25].

4. EVALUATION AND PERFORMANCE

The system was tested on a MacAir 11-inch, macOS 10.13, with a 1,3 GHz Intel Core i5 processor, 4 GB RAM and an Intel HD Graphics 5000 1536 MB GPU. The connection was instant and without any technical difficulties, and the motion detector’s response to the aforementioned operating system was satisfactory without substantial delays, despite the fact that system used was just above the minimum for the motion detector’s recommendations.

The proposed configuration between gestures and pitch-shifted semitones (for the Harmonizer Processor) during the system’s field testing, is shown in Table 1. The handling of the system, as proved in the demonstration, was natural and easy, reliable and with very few milliseconds of delay (20 ms), making Polyfōnía suitable for live performances. The demonstration video of the system can be found here ² [25].

¹ drive.google.com/drive/folders/16n3seCv_5daH0azoDbSIosBYmIcZvdda
² drive.google.com/drive/folders/1efiOdRANiiN_ax2FoaN4WS5_RXAI2Pe-

Figure 5. Polyfonia modules' gestures

Figure 6. The Harmonizer Interaction module activates the fourteen voices toggles.

For the evaluation of the Polyfonia's Live Looping Module, the gestures "Record" and "Play" (Figure 5) were evaluated, performing 100 repetitions for each gesture, achieving both 100% accuracy. For the evaluation of the Polyfonia's Harmonizer Module, a confusion matrix was created. The system was intentionally tested in poor light conditions. Due to symmetry, only the left side was examined, for a right-handed user, for the seven gestures (Table 1, Figure 5) and the no-gesture (0). For each gesture 100 repetitions were performed. Figure 7 shows the confusion matrix. The overall accuracy of the Polyfonia is 0.945, computed by dividing the total number of true positives over the total number of tests.

Polyfonia was presented for a first time in a solo-performance, of the XXX Festival, funded by YYY. A video containing a part of this live performance can be found here³ [25]. In the first live performance of the system, due to the lack of (in-ear) monitoring [35], the performer uses the screen for checking the loops and different voices activation. In similar cases, a projection of the feedback behind the public could be used. During the performance, both of the Polyfonia modules were used (live-looping and harmonizer). The performance took place after the sunset, with stage lighting, and it was resonated by the audience in a very positive way. The response of the system was very good, as no problems or substantial delays were observed. The system can't follow extremely fast hand movements but it is fully suitable for use in vocal polyphonic singing, and for any performance that does not require extremely quick changes in polyphonic singing patterns. As stated by a conductor which was present at the Polyfonia's first performance, its delay may even seem natural, as it is similar to the natural response of a choir in a conductor's gestures.

5. FUTURE WORK

Polyfonia could be enriched with new movements as well as with additional vocal processors. An interesting field of research is a kinesiological study for the control of many more parameters and functions, maintaining simplicity and

³ drive.google.com/file/d/1YqPztgA1bfeLfBc5VZYrXo02fZjgwZCO/view

		TRUE							
		II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	O
PREDICTED	II	96	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
	III	0	97	0	0	2	2	0	0
	IV	0	0	97	0	4	0	0	0
	V	0	0	0	89	0	0	0	0
	VI	0	0	0	0	87	0	0	2
	VII	0	0	0	0	0	91	0	1
	VIII	0	0	0	0	0	0	96	2
	O	4	3	3	11	7	7	4	92

Figure 7. Polyfōnía’s confusion matrix

Figure 8. Performing with Polyfōnía.

clarity in its handling. Continuous control of the effects could be added, offering e.g. time shifting for the loops of the Live-looping Interaction module and volume or other effects automation for the Harmonizer Interaction Module.

The Live-looping Interaction module, could be developed to record more tracks enabling loop hierarchy manipulation. The Harmonizer Interaction Module could also be combined with an automatic harmonization system for specific music genres, e.g., a pretrained deep neural network. The performer could then control the degree of intervention of the automatic harmonization with gestures or set up the starting values. Moreover, a pretrained neural network in polyphonic music could also be embedded as an automatic harmonizing continuator, to take the performer’s intended use of harmony as input in order to imitate the performer’s

aesthetics.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The control of vocal processors without pedals, knobs, gloves or wiring, may open up new horizons in vocal performance, enabling the use of processors in either demanding configurations, theatrical settings or expressive restrictions and requirements. The simplicity of Polyfōnía’s use, coupled with the absence of equipment and combined with the sound enrichment that processors provide, can create a liberating contrast with a variety of applications and unexplored features.

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